

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

PERFORMANCE REPORT IN INTEGRATED REPORTING

Liudmila Khoruzhy¹, Tatyana Gupalova¹, Valery Khoruzhiy²

¹Russian State Agrarian University – MAA named after K.A. Timiryazev, Moscow, Russia,

²Institute of Economics and Crisis Management, Moscow, Russia.

Article Received: March 2019

Accepted: April 2019

Published: May 2019

Abstract:

The article proposes a special grouping of information about the modifications of the capital involved by the firm. The form of the performance report we designed is designed to provide stakeholders with information on market valuation of agro-industrial firms for their actual adherence to natural and ecological, social, industrial and industrial, biological, financial, intellectual and human values policies that form an increase or outflow of capital. Compliance with the firm's management of the policies adopted will be reflected in the performance report as an increase in capital in the form of sums for improving the safety and quality of life of people, including bonuses, bonuses, dividends, mandatory and voluntary social contributions, subsidies, taxes and other social payments, type of funds for environmental management, maintenance and restoration of the environment, in the amounts of financial investments and profitable investments in excess of their nominal value, in the calculation of interest on loans and loans, profit, dividends, interest and other financial income, in a positive amount from the revaluation of intangible and intellectual assets, other assets in a fair assessment, from investments in staff education, from revaluation of buildings, structures, machinery, equipment and other industrial - production resources, from the revaluation of biological assets. If the company fails to comply with the policies regarding the accepted values, capital outflow will be received, which will result in accrued fines and other sanctions for violating the law on ensuring decent working conditions and pay for it, for violating environmental legislation, in a negative amount of revaluation of intangible assets, and also in losses from unregistered trademarks and other objects of intellectual property, in the presence of a negative amount of revaluation of objects of industrial production bases funds, in maintaining financial investments below their nominal value, in fines and other sanctions for violations of economic contracts, in the presence of losses from marriage in production, damage and loss of material values, and in reporting agricultural producers there will also be a negative amount from the revaluation of biological assets, write-off of the value of dead livestock, dead farm animals and plants. It is proposed to form a report on the basis of structured accounting information.

Keywords: *accounting, value added, capital, strategy.*

Corresponding author:**Liudmila Khoruzhy**

Russian State Agrarian University – MAA named after K.A. Timiryazev,
Moscow, Russia.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Liudmila Khoruzhy et al., **Performance Report In Integrated Reporting.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION:

The International Standard for Integrated Reporting [1] recommends a modification of six types of capital: financial, industrial, intellectual, human, social and reputational, and natural. At the same time for agribusiness firms, rather, it is better to talk about such varieties of capital as:

- financial capital (funds of debt and equity financing, grants and funds from production and financial activities that the organization has);
- intellectual and human capital (competence and loyalty of the organization's employees, their abilities and experience, ethical standards and motivation adopted in the organization, that is, incentives that encourage the organization's employees to be actively productive, since the growth of qualifications and education of the employees of agro-industrial organizations and now are a prerequisite for the growth of production efficiency and labor productivity);
- social capital (values accumulated by customers, suppliers, business partners, representatives of local communities, legislative and regulatory bodies and persons interacting with the reporting firm; realizing social responsibility of business to society, agribusiness companies pay social insurance contributions, as well as provide support health care facilities, science, culture and sports in the regions where your business operates);
- natural-ecological capital (values in renewable and non-renewable natural environment resources, including air, water, land for non-agricultural use, minerals, forests, biological diversity and ecosystem well-being as part of a world consisting of particles and subparticles that are dependent on each other);
- industrial production capital (buildings, structures, equipment available for production and business activities, investments in which are necessary for the creation and modernization of fixed assets and other industrial production objects);
- biological capital (the most important category for agricultural producers, which includes agricultural land, farm animals, agricultural crops) [2].

It is important that owners of capital invest in the maintenance and development of certain values and they are interested in effective tools for assessing the investment attractiveness of companies [3-9]. At the same time, a firm can adhere to both positive and negative values in its strategies [10]. The selected values will determine the system of semantic axes of the company's activities, which, in turn, will determine the modification of capital in the reporting period. But the integrated reporting standard does not provide a form for presenting information on capital modifications in the course of a firm's activity and

therefore an organizational and methodological development of this issue is required.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The problem of structuring information about the size and modifications of various types of capital to substantiate the investment attractiveness of the company was investigated by MA Vakhrushin [3], V.G. Getman [4; 5], E.I. Kostyukova [6], N. Yu. Tryascina [7], N.S. Plaskova, N.A. Prodanova and others [8; 9].

A philosophical approach to the analysis of positive and negative values was proposed by T. Adorno [10]. M.L. Pyatov [11; 12], T.N. Nightingale, A.S. Sorokina, A.A. Gusniev [12], N.V. Filippova, R.G. Ahmadeev, O.A. Bukanova, L.A. Tchaikovsky [13] investigated the positive role of the financial and non-financial information of the company in the social space. Formation of information on the activities of agribusiness firms, including the formation of integrated reporting, is investigated by R.A. Alborov, S.M. Kontsevaya, S.V. Kozmenkova [14], L.I. Horuzhy [7; 15], I.G. Stefan, L.A. Zimakova, M.A. Vakhrushina, I.B. Malitskaya and others [16].

But for all the value of the results of the research, the question of reflecting information on capital modifications in the formation of integrated reporting by agro-industrial firms requires an organizational and methodological study.

The purpose of the study is to determine the appropriate grouping of information in the integrated reporting of capital modifications used by agribusiness firms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In the course of the company's activity, the capital invested is modified and it is important for the owners of financial, intellectual, human, social, natural-ecological, industrial-production, biological capital to see the influx and outflow of all types of capital.

Investments in intellectual, human, social, natural-ecological, biological, industrial-industrial and financial values will lead to the inflow or outflow of capital in the course of the company's activities and interactions. Capital has a relationship with the values of the company, which can be represented in such a way that the intellectual-human, social, natural-ecological, biological, industrial-industrial and financial values are manifested in the intellectual-human, social, natural-ecological, biological, industrial and financial capitals.

The growth of various types of capital shows the organization following the values of development (Table 1).

Table 1: Capital Gains in Development Values (authoring)

Development values	Capital inflow
Financial	Amount in financial investments and profitable investments in excess of their nominal value; accrued interest on loans and loans
Industrial production	Positive amount of revaluation of buildings, structures, equipment
Biological	Positive revaluation of biological assets
Intellectually human	The amount of revaluation of intangible assets; the amount of capital due to deviations in the value of assets at a fair and historical assessment
Social	Accrued amounts for improving the safety and quality of life and work of employees and participants of the organization, including bonuses, dividends, amounts for compulsory and voluntary social contributions, subsidies, taxes to the budget and extra-budgetary funds
Natural-ecological	Voluntary deductions for environmental management, maintenance and restoration of ecology

Capital outflows occur as a result, most often, of the unconscious orientation of the firm's management towards degradation values (Table 2).

Table 2: Capital outflow in degradation values (authoring)

Values of degradation	Capital outflow
Natural-ecological	Amounts of accrued fines and other sanctions for violation of environmental legislation
Social	The amount of accrued fines and other sanctions for violation of the legislation on ensuring decent working conditions and its payment
Industrial production	Negative amount of revaluation of fixed assets
Biological	The negative amount of revaluation of biological assets; value of dead livestock, dead animals
Financial	The amount in financial investments and profitable investments below their nominal value; the amount of accrued fines and other sanctions for violations of economic contracts; the cost of losses from marriage in production, damage and loss of material values
Intellectually human	The negative amount of the revaluation of intangible assets; the amount of losses from unregistered trademarks and other intellectual property

To demonstrate the correlation between the values of the company and the inflow and outflow of capital, we offer a performance report developed by us, which reflects the dynamic processes of capital modification. Sales revenue, reduced by the cost of maintaining capital, will show an increase or outflow of various types of capital (table 3).

Social capital gains will be expressed in accrued amounts to improve the safety and quality of life of people, including bonuses, dividends, mandatory and voluntary social contributions, subsidies, taxes to the budget and other social benefits for company employees. Social capital investments in the construction and modernization of social, educational, social and social facilities and service infrastructure, including the construction of

houses, healthcare facilities, physical culture and sports, schools, kindergartens, sanatoriums and other investments in improving the quality of life of people rational taxation [2; 4; 13].

The growth of natural-ecological capital is expressed in contributions to the rational use of natural resources, the maintenance and restoration of the environment as part of taxes to the budget and extra-budgetary funds, as well as charity. This is facilitated by investments in natural and environmental values and the maintenance of activities using low-waste and non-waste production facilities for gas and dust collection, water treatment, anti-erosion and anti-mud facilities, for the protection of wild animals, fish, birds, plants [6; 9].

Growth of financial capital comes from financial investments and profitable investments above their nominal value, when calculating interest on loans and borrowings, making profits, dividends, interest and other financial income.

The growth of intellectual and human capital is projected when revaluation of intangible and intellectual assets, from deviations in asset values at a

fair and historical assessment, from investments in personnel education and other investments in intellectual and human values. The amount of expenditure on training, training and retraining of personnel of the company, as well as the cost of certification and counseling of workers increases intellectual and human capital and decreases financial capital [12; 15].

Table 3: Proposed structure of the performance report in the integrated reporting of agro-industrial organizations (authoring)

Indicators
Sales revenue (with value added tax, excise taxes, etc.)
Expenses for reimbursement of capital - total, including:
The cost of maintaining the operational properties and operation of machinery, equipment, buildings, structures, biological assets, intangible assets
Wages in accordance with contracts (without bonuses and other incentive payments)
Legally prescribed mandatory costs of environmental management and maintaining a normal ecology
Other
Capital gains - total, including:
Social (accrued amounts for improving the safety and quality of life and work of employees and participants of the organization, including bonuses, bonuses, dividends, mandatory and voluntary social contributions, subsidies, taxes to the budget, etc.)
Natural and environmental (deductions for environmental management, maintenance and restoration of ecology)
Financial (amount in financial investments and profitable investments above their nominal value; accrued interest on loans and borrowings, making a profit, dividends, interest and other income, etc.)
Intellectual-human (the amount of revaluation of intangible - intellectual assets; the amount of capital due to deviations in the value of assets at a fair and historical assessment, investments in staff education, etc.)
Industrial production (positive amount of revaluation of buildings, structures, machinery and equipment)
Biological (positive amount of biological asset revaluation)
Capital outflows - total, including:
Social (amount of accrued fines and other sanctions for violation of the legislation on ensuring decent working conditions and pay for it)
Natural and environmental (the amount of accrued fines and other sanctions for violation of environmental legislation)
Financial (amount in financial investments and profitable investments below their nominal value; the amount of accrued fines and other sanctions for violations of business contracts; the cost of losses from marriage in production, damage and loss of wealth)
Intellectual-human (negative amount of revaluation of intangible assets; amount of losses from unregistered trademarks and other intellectual property)
Industrial production (negative amount of revaluation of fixed assets)
Biological (negative amount of biological asset revaluation; value of dead livestock, dead farm animals and plants)
Total increase / outflow (+ / -) of capital
Social
Natural-ecological
Financial
Intellectually human
Industrial production
Biological

The increase in industrial-production capital will occur from a positive amount of revaluation of buildings, structures, machinery, equipment and other industrial-production resources. And the firm's

strategy plays a proven role [9; 16].

The increase in biological capital is a positive amount of revaluation of biological assets, which is facilitated

by investments in the restoration of agricultural land, terracing of steep slopes, and other improvements in unproductive farmland and breeding work with farm animals and plants [2; 14].

The outflow of social capital is due to the accrual of fines and other sanctions for violation of the law on ensuring decent working conditions and its payment. The outflow of natural-ecological capital is, most often, the sum of accrued fines and other sanctions for violation of environmental legislation. Financial capital outflow is the amount in financial investments and profitable investments below their nominal value, as well as the amount of accrued fines and other sanctions for violations of business contracts or the cost of losses from marriage in production, damage and loss of material values. The outflow of intellectual human capital is a negative amount of revaluation of intangible assets, as well as the amount of losses from unregistered trademarks and other intellectual property. The outflow of industrial-production capital will be fixed if there is a negative amount of revaluation of fixed assets. The outflow of biological capital will occur with a negative amount of revaluation of biological assets of the value of dead cattle, dead farm animals and plants.

Thus, the stakeholder will be presented in a structured way as the market valuation of the company's activities (through sales revenue), and the actual adherence to the policies of following certain values in the company's activities.

CONCLUSION:

In integrated reporting, a special grouping of information on modifications of all types of capital involved is appropriate. A performance report form specially designed by us will help provide information to a wide range of interested users of integrated reporting on dynamic capital formation processes in strategically important development areas for determining the economic, environmental and social performance of agribusiness firms. Stakeholders will be presented in a structured form as a market assessment of the company, and the actual compliance with the policy of following the natural and environmental, social, industrial and industrial, biological, financial, intellectual and human values, which form the growth or outflow of capital in the reporting period.

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